

Occurrence of *Euconnus pragensis* MACHULKA in Wrocław, Poland (Coleoptera: Staphylinidae: Scydmaeninae)

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PAWEŁ JAŁOSZYŃSKI

Museum of Natural History, University of Wrocław, Sienkiewicza 21, 50-335 Wrocław, Poland,
e-mail: scydmaenus@yahoo.com, ORCID: 0000-0003-2973-1803

ABSTRACT. Occurrence of *Euconnus pragensis* MACHULKA in Wrocław, Poland (Coleoptera: Staphylinidae: Scydmaeninae).

Only one confirmed record of *Euconnus pragensis* is known so far from Poland. A rich new collecting site in the Pilczycki Forest within the city of Wrocław, SW Poland, is reported, with ten specimens found on merely two occasions in 2018 and 2024.

KEY WORDS: Staphylinoidea, Stenichnini, Poland.

INTRODUCTION

JAŁOSZYŃSKI *et al.* (2015) demonstrated that the only record of *Euconnus pragensis* MACHULKA, 1923 for Poland included in the Catalogue of the Fauna of Poland (BURAKOWSKI *et al.* 1978; abbreviated as CFP) was based on three problematic sources and is not reliable. The authors of CFP cited NERESHEIMER & WAGNER (1940) who give a collecting site in Brieselang, which is located in Germany. The second reference in CFP is that of NERESHEIMER & WAGNER (1942), where *E. pragensis* was reported from environs of Frankfurt (Oder), a German city situated on the western bank of the Oder River, opposite the Polish town of Słubice. Słubice (German name: Dammvorstadt) until 1945 was a part of Frankfurt. This caused the 1942 record being cited in the Polish literature as environs of Słubice, and consequently including *E. pragensis* into the fauna of Poland. The third source cited in CFP is HORION (1949), who simply repeats the previous data.

JAŁOSZYŃSKI *et al.* (2015) concluded that it was not possible to deduce whether the collecting site reported in NERESHEIMER & WAGNER (1942) is in Germany or in Poland. JAŁOSZYŃSKI *et al.* (2015) also suggested that because the name Dammvorstadt (or Frankfurt/Oder-Dammvorstadt) was not cited in the German-language paper, it may be interpreted as a record from the area west of Oder, and not within the current territory of Poland.

For the above reasons, the only certain record of *Euconnus pragensis* in Poland was that of JAŁOSZYŃSKI *et al.* (2015), who reported a single specimen collected in the reserve Góra Miłek near Wojcieszów (UTM code WS64) in the West Sudety Mountains.

A new collecting site of *Euconnus pragensis*:

– **Lower Silesia:** XS36, Wrocław Kozanów, Pilczycki Forest, 2 IX 2018, 4 exx., 29 VI 2024, 6 exx., all collected by sifting leaf litter in degenerated deciduous forest near Oder, mainly around old oak and elm trees and partly rotten logs, leg. & coll. P. Jałoszyński.

DISCUSSION

Euconnus pragensis belongs in the nominotypical subgenus, and is a member of the *E. claviger* species group, which includes some of species previously placed in *Napochus* THOMSON, 1859. JAŁOSZYŃSKI (2021) placed *Napochus* as a junior synonym of *Euconnus* s. str. The *E. claviger* species group is characterized by a subconical pronotum, broadest at base and strongly narrowing anteriorly, and a sharply delimited, loosely assembled tetramerous antennal club. The two species of this group that occur in Poland, *E. pragensis* (Figs 1–3) and *E. claviger* (MÜLLER & KUNZE, 1822) (Figs 4–6) are similar to each other. They can be unambiguously distinguished by a clearly different shape of the head, different proportions of antennomeres, and the aedeagi. *Euconnus pragensis* is believed to be a more warm-loving species, and is distributed in (alphabetically) Austria, Azerbaijan, Czech Rep., Denmark, Finland, France, Great Britain, Germany, Hungary, Italy, Poland, Portugal (Madeira), Slovakia, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland, and Ukraine (SCHÜLKE & SMETANA 2015). A similar *Euconnus* s. str. that occurs in Poland is *E. maklinii* (MANNERHEIM, 1844) (formerly in the subgenus *Neonapochus* MACHULKA, 1929), but males of this species have strongly asymmetrical antennal clubs and it is unlikely to confuse *E. maklinii* with *E. pragensis*.

The new locality in Wrocław is surprisingly rich, with only two collecting occasions yielding ten specimens from less than a half kilogram of sifted remains of leaf litter. The only co-occurring scydmaenine species in these samples was the common *Euconnus pubicollis* (MÜLLER & KUNZE, 1822). This finding may mean that *E. pragensis* has recently colonized new places in Poland, possibly dispersing from the south, or that it has been overlooked for the past hundred years. Certainly, it was not found in relatively intensively surveyed Wrocław and surrounding areas by the pre-war pioneers of Silesian coleopterology, whose rich collections are curated at the Museum of Natural History, University of Wrocław (JAŁOSZYŃSKI *et al.* 2014).

It seems possible that *E. pragensis* might have been misidentified as *E. claviger* and some records from Poland may in fact refer to the former species. *Euconnus claviger* has been recorded from most of the territory of Poland (see distribution at https://baza.biomap.pl/pl/taxon/species-euconnus_claviger_claviger/default/tr/y), and modern records of this species are more numerous than those for e.g., *Scydmorephes minutus* (CHAUDOIR, 1845). However, during my extensive study of Scydmaeninae of Poland, I have collected *S. minutus* more frequently than *E. claviger*. Voucher specimens require verification, especially those used for large survey projects where only species names recorded from the area under study are published, without exact collecting data, and difficult groups of beetles have not been identified by specialists. It may turn out that *E. pragensis*, so richly occurring in Wrocław, is more common in Poland than the current literature suggests.

An alternative hypothesis is that Wrocław and adjacent areas offer preferable conditions for at least some thermophiles. A common and abundant occurrence in and around Wrocław of the otherwise rare *Scydmaenus hellwigii* (HERBST, 1792) supports this view. Although found on other localities in various regions of Poland (see e.g., CMOLUCH 1987, JAŁOSZYŃSKI 2003, and a distribution map at https://baza.biomap.pl/pl/taxon/species-scydmaenus_hellwigii/default/tr/y), it is most common in Lower Silesia. Around

Wrocław, dozens of individuals of *S. hellwigii* can be easily found under bark of dying trees inhabited by *Lasius* ants. On one occasion, a hundred of individuals were counted under barks of old deciduous trees, most of them found under bark of a single dying lime tree (JAŁOSZYŃSKI *et al.* 2015). This rich occurrence made it possible for JAŁOSZYŃSKI & KILIAN (2012) to obtain a larva of this species by rearing adults collected in Wrocław. In no other region of Poland *S. hellwigii* can be collected so easily and in so large numbers, suggesting that Wrocław indeed is an unusual enclave for some species. The occurrence of *E. pragensis*, therefore, may be attributed to the unique environmental conditions of Wrocław and adjacent areas. Future field work and verifications of published but poorly documented records of the similar *E. claviger* will help understand the true distribution and population dynamics of *E. pragensis* in Poland.

It is also worth mentioning that two more species of the *E. claviger* group can be expected to occur in Poland. *Euconnus chrysocomus* (SAULCY, 1864) and *E. campestris* (SCHAUFUSS, 1866) occur in Germany and Czech Republic, and it seems plausible to find them both in Poland.

Figs. 1–6. *Euconnus pragensis* (1–3) and *E. claviger* (4–6). Dorsal habitus (1, 4), aedeagus in ventral view (2, 5), and antenna (3, 6) (fot. P. Jałoszyński).

Ryc. 1–6. *Euconnus pragensis* (1–3) i *E. claviger* (4–6). Habitus (1, 4), edeagus w rzucie brzuszny (2, 5) oraz czułęk (3, 6) (photos P. Jałoszyński).

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STRESZCZENIE

**Występowanie *Euconnus pragensis* MACHULKA we Wrocławiu, Polska
(Coleoptera: Staphylinidae: Scydmaeninae)**

Cytowane w *Katalogu fauny Polski* dane dotyczące występowania *E. pragensis* MACHULKA najprawdopodobniej dotyczą obecnego terytorium Niemiec. Jedynym pewnym polskim stanowiskiem była dotychczas Góra Miłek ad Wojcieszów w Sudetach Zachodnich, skąd znany jest jeden okaz. W latach 2018 i 2024 odłowiono dziesięć osobników tego gatunku w Lesie Pilczyckim w obrębie Wrocławia, co sugeruje, że jest to wyjątkowe stanowisko w skali kraju. *Euconnus pragensis* jest chrząszczem ciepłolubnym i nie był poławiany w okolicach Wrocławia przez przedwojennych pionierów śląskiej koleopterologii, których zbiory znajdują się w Muzeum Przyrodniczym Uniwersytetu Wrocławskiego. Może to sugerować niedawną dyspersję z południa. Nie można jednak wykluczyć, że ze względu na duże podobieństwo *E. pragensis* i *E. claviger* (MÜLLER & KUNZE), część opublikowanych i dość licznych rekordów tego drugiego gatunku to wynik błędu w identyfikacji.

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